

FPN networks for seamless segmentation on Ultra96-v2.

The Problem

The problem statement is the need for scientists to conserve caribou populations through the deployment of IoT Earth Cam units using Raspberry Pi 4 and Wyze outdoor cameras. The goal is to acquire data on the caribou population and their behavior, as well as monitor their habitat to inform conservation efforts. The system will also utilize a LORA HAT for long-range communication and Azure-based data acquisition for efficient data management and analysis. The challenge is to design and implement a reliable and effective system that can withstand harsh environmental conditions and provide valuable data for caribou conservation.

The Project Plan

The Project Plan for implementing an IoT Earth Cam system using Wyze cameras and Raspberry Pi 4 to aid in caribou conservation in northern BC, Canada, could include the following steps:

1. **Research and Site Selection:** Conduct research on caribou habitats and migration patterns in northern BC, Canada, and identify potential sites for installing the IoT Earth Cam system. Consult with local experts and stakeholders to ensure that the system is placed in areas that will provide valuable data for caribou conservation.
2. **Material Procurement:** Source and procure the necessary materials for the IoT Earth Cam system, including Raspberry Pi 4, Wyze Cam 3, LORA HAT, and other necessary components.
3. **System Design:** Design the IoT Earth Cam system, including the placement and orientation of the cameras, the deployment of the LORA HAT for long-range communication, and the use of Azure-based data acquisition for efficient data management and analysis.
4. **System Installation:** Install the IoT Earth Cam system at selected sites in northern BC, Canada. Ensure that the system is installed securely and can withstand harsh environmental conditions.
5. **System Testing:** Conduct system testing to ensure that the cameras are capturing high-quality footage and that the LORA HAT is functioning properly. Test the

Azure-based data acquisition system to ensure that data is being collected and managed efficiently.

6. Data Analysis: Analyze the data collected by the IoT Earth Cam system to identify trends and patterns in caribou behavior and habitat use. Use this data to inform conservation efforts and develop strategies for protecting caribou populations in northern BC, Canada.
7. Documentation and Reporting: Document the entire process of implementing the IoT Earth Cam system, including site selection, system design, installation, testing, and data analysis. Prepare a report on the findings of the study and present the report to stakeholders and the scientific community.

Overall, the goal of this project plan is to implement a reliable and effective system for monitoring caribou populations in northern BC, Canada, using IoT Earth Cam units and Raspberry Pi 4. Through careful site selection, system design, and data analysis, this system can provide valuable insights into caribou behavior and habitat use to aid in conservation efforts.

Research

Caribou (*Rangifer tarandus*) are an important species for both indigenous communities and ecosystems across the Northern Hemisphere. They are known for their unique vocalizations, which can communicate various messages such as mating calls, alarm calls, and social bonding calls. These vocalizations are important for caribou communication and survival, and can also provide valuable data for researchers studying caribou populations.

However, gathering data on caribou vocalizations can be challenging due to the remoteness of their habitat and the difficulty of observing and recording their behavior. As a result, there is a need for reliable and efficient methods of collecting and analyzing caribou vocalization data.

The use of IoT technology, such as Raspberry Pi 4 and Wyze outdoor cameras, offers a promising solution for collecting caribou vocalization data. By placing cameras in strategic locations and using sound-recording devices, researchers can capture and categorize caribou vocalizations, which can provide insights into their behavior and habitat use.

The creation of a caribou vocalization data set using IoT technology can provide valuable data for researchers studying caribou populations. This data set can be used to identify vocalization patterns and trends, which can inform conservation efforts and help protect caribou populations from threats such as habitat loss and climate change.

Overall, the creation of a caribou vocalization data set using IoT technology offers a promising solution for gathering data on caribou populations, and can provide valuable insights into their behavior and habitat use to inform conservation efforts.

System Design

Image: Block diagram

Image: PCB Design

Image: Wearable Chassis design

Image: Software Design

Image: Power supply design

Material Procurement

imageMaterial needed for the project will be sourced and procured

System Build

Image: Electronics build, Mechanical Build, Software programming

Developmental Testing

Image: System electrical testing, System software testing, System mechanical testing

System Application Tests

Image: The system will be used to audit my environment

Documentation & Conclusions

Image: Each of the project plan tasks will include a related blog

System Concept

Credentials

I have participated successfully in several element14 design challenges and complex Road Tests. These projects are referenced to demonstrate how fully I participate in Design Challenges, my level of technical capabilities and the diligence of my blog postings.

Summary & Notes

In summary, the creation of a caribou vocalization data set using IoT technology such as Raspberry Pi 4 and Wyze outdoor cameras can offer a promising solution for gathering data on caribou populations. By recording and categorizing caribou vocalizations, researchers can gain insights into their behavior and habitat use, which can inform conservation efforts and help protect caribou populations from threats such as habitat loss and climate change.

However, gathering such data can be challenging due to the remoteness of caribou habitats and the difficulty of observing and recording their behavior. Therefore, careful planning and selection of recording sites is crucial to ensure accurate and representative data collection.

It is important to note that the creation of a caribou vocalization data set using IoT technology is just one piece of the puzzle when it comes to caribou conservation efforts. It is crucial to consider a holistic approach that takes into account factors such as habitat protection, climate change mitigation, and indigenous knowledge and perspectives.